

Who's Polluting the Hoosier Air? An Examination of International versus Domestic Industry Operating in Indiana

Introduction

The unstable US economy has forced many executives to make the difficult decision to close factories and set up operations elsewhere to take advantage of low-wages and better business environments. The loss of production jobs has been particularly economically devastating in the traditionally manufacturing-based areas of the country (Teaford, 1994). The Rust Belt, often referred to as the Manufacturing Belt, consists of northern Midwestern and Northeastern US states, generally from Iowa to Pennsylvania (Lopez, 2004). These states' economies were built on manufacturing during the industry's boom, but with the nationwide shift to service and high-tech industries, they face great challenges in reshaping their economies and retraining their workforces to better handle the realities of the global marketplace (Florida, 1996). The most production-intensive state in the US is Indiana, where one in six residents (nicknamed "Hoosiers") hold jobs in manufacturing (Charles & Hicks, 2008). As a result of the recent economic downturn and other factors, Indiana's economy has struggled when industry-based jobs have been lost because there is little readily available employment to replace them (Evanoff & Russell, 2008).

Reliance on industry in an economy often comes with other challenges, namely air pollution. Indiana has typically been a conservative, manufacturing-based, pro-business state, and attitudes produced by these positions often stand in contrast to environmental standards (Schreiber, 1997). For example, the steel-producing city of Gary had a long history of neglecting environmental concerns in favor of economic progress. Its local government had established a precedent of noninterference with US Steel's operations and although local steel owners knew that their "social costs of industrial pollution impinged upon the entire urban population" (Hurley, 1995, p. 15), they did not take action to protect the local ecology because it would hurt their bottom line.

Indiana has had comparatively worse environmental degradation compared to other states. In 2004, Indiana ranked as the 29th highest nation or state in greenhouse gas air emissions, polluting at 59.9 million metric tons of carbon equivalent, meaning that Indiana produced more pollution than countries like the Netherlands, Argentina, Venezuela, and even the traditionally industrial state of Michigan (Rabe, 2004).

Along with the rest of the country, Indiana has lost many factory jobs within the past generation, and to offset this manufacturing job loss, state agents have attempted to market the state as a pro-business destination for foreign manufacturing (Overby, 2007), ultimately receiving pledges from multinationals to create factory jobs. The majority of global capital in Indiana (and nationwide) is dedicated to industry, especially new commitments (Anderson & Zeile, 2009).

The competition to attract foreign capital and investment to an American locale has intensified, and as a result, more focus and pressure have been placed upon statewide agents to bring home those jobs at any cost (Sapat, 2004). Because an organizational focus of the IEDC has been to create incentives for companies to engage in business in Indiana, as well as the fact that Indiana has been less proactive than other states when it comes to enacting and enforcing environmental regulations, it is understandable then that Hoosiers might be concerned if aggressive strategies by state economic development officials result in foreign manufacturing engaging in activities that could threaten the local air quality. As such, the importance of manufacturing for the health of the statewide economy as well as the increasing reliance on foreign industry to replenish those jobs will be a central theme of this study, which will focus on air pollution rates of multinational manufacturers operating in Indiana.

Research Question

No matter who creates it, environmental degradation of the air becomes the problem of local citizens - This is known as the tragedy of the commons, a dilemma in which various individuals or entities, acting in their own self-interests, will eventually deplete a resource shared by all (Hardin, 1968). Because industrial production and the assembly of goods tend to be pollution-heavy, it is reasonable to inquire about the levels of air pollution by global companies operating in Indiana. This is of concern especially to those who live in Indiana because environmental initiatives and proactive environmental regulations have not historically been key components of Indiana state leadership, which instead has simply followed the lead of national legislation. Results of this inquiry might then lead to an exploration of the potential conflicting interest of marketing the state to international industry and job growth facilitated by state agents at the potential expense of stringent pollution oversight.

When a multinational corporation establishes its production operations in a host country, to which environmental laws and standards do those manufacturing facilities adhere? Many firms take the position that ethics are culturally determined and therefore they are justified in adopting the ethics and laws of the cultures in which they operate. In essence, the adage, “When in Rome, do as the Romans do” tends to be the applicable mantra for doing business in global relationships (Moon & Woolliams, 2000). This arrangement is often followed when multinational companies operate in underdeveloped countries where pollution regulations are less rigorous and can be taken advantage of (Shrader-Frechette, 1991). However, whether this holds true if a multinational company from an industrialized country operates in an American state with less stringent air emission standards has not yet been explored.

Has the lack of stringent national environmental regulatory laws allowed pro-business states such as Indiana with a traditional emphasis on manufacturing and a lack of focus on environmental legislation to attract multinational industry at the expense of local air quality? An assessment of the air emission rates of domestic versus multinational industrialists operating in Indiana would shed some light on this inquiry.

Background and History

Conservation, or environmentalism, began as a social movement and gained attention in 1962 with the release of Rachel Carson’s *Silent Spring*, which detailed environmental impacts of releasing chemicals into the air. This attention grew as the first “Earth Day” was celebrated in 1970 in order to bring awareness of environmentalism in America (Landau, 2002). Since then, other areas of the world have initiated environmentalism at their own rates. Ecological modernization theory explains how industrialized countries individually react to environmental-related concerns in their locales (Buttel, 2000). In particular, it indicates that environmental legislation and regulation enforcement are affected by governmental organization, citizen demands, social movements, technological innovations, voting patterns, special interest groups, non-governmental organizations, government proxies and institutions, and the number of regulatory failures in the region as well as an array of additional factors that can increase or decrease the pace of environmental progression (Redclift, 2010). Differences in regional environmental laws are based on unique social mores and local cultural variations which dictate the evolution of governmental legislation and the implementation of environmental regulations (Bell, Bell, & Carolan, 2008). Because social and regulatory reforms undertaken by societies generally tend to change at different rates depending on a variety of

external factors, these variables become incorporated as integral themes of ecological modernization theory (Mol & Sonnenfeld, 2000).

Since around 1990, many important European Union (EU) consumer and environmental regulations have been more precautionary than their American counterparts (Vogel, 2003). Although environmental legislation was initiated slowly, current EU environmental policy is now more stringent than most national laws in Europe. In 1997 at the UN Conference on Climate Change, the EU led a goal-setting commitment of reducing greenhouse emissions and advanced the Kyoto Protocol, an initiative aimed at reducing global warming, which the US ultimately decided not to ratify (Oberthur & Ott, 1999). In addition, the Basel Convention of Hazardous Wastes had been ratified by every EU member state by 1994 but still has not been ratified by the US, and both the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity and the 2000 Biosafety Protocol were signed by the EU, but not by the United States (Vogel, 2003).

Like the EU, Japan has initiated its own environmental reforms. In 1993, Japan took a progressive domestic approach toward the environment which included pollution control and industrial emission regulations (Dauvergne, 2009). By the mid-1990s, Japan had made their own “significant contribution to the ecological modernization debate by unpacking the Japanese environmental experience” (Barrett, 2005).

There has been an opposite trend in the US. From the 1960s through the mid-1980s, American environmental regulatory standards were more stringent, comprehensive, and innovative than the standards of any individual European country (Drezner, 2008). The last major legislative expansion of federal environmental regulation in the US took place in 1990 with the enactment of three statutes: the Oil Pollution Act, the Pollution Prevention Act, and the Clean Air Act Amendments (Vogel, 2003). In the late 1990s, Indiana and fifteen other states passed legislation or resolutions that were highly critical of the Kyoto Protocol and opposed ratification of it by the US Senate (Rabe, 2004).

Not only do nations enact environmental legislation at different paces, but American states progress on environmental concerns at their own individual rates (Smickt, 2008). As a result, environmental regulations in the US are often dictated on a state-by-state basis (Rabe, 2004). A new phenomenon known as the devolution revolution has emerged in which state governments have established or reestablished themselves as powerful entities capable of spending time and effort on specific regulations and policymaking (Gerber & Teske, 2000). As a result,

in recent years greater environmental regulatory responsibility in several US lawmaking areas has moved from federal to state government.

For many regulatory policies, the federal government establishes broad policy objectives and parameters while state governments serve as the key implementing agents (Gerber & Teske, 2000). For example, the federal government has considerable authority and discretion in regulating areas such as worker safety. However, in other policy arenas, including occupational regulation and insurance regulation standards, states have more or even complete jurisdiction (Keller & Levinson, 2002). Recently, states' rights have been increasing in key legislation areas such as medicinal marijuana and gay marriage (Singh, 2003), and Donovan, Mooney, and Smith (2009) indicated that local and state governments currently have a greater impact on the daily lives of Americans today than the federal government.

The saying "all politics is local" is often used in the United States political arena to express the notion that voters tend to support candidates for state, county, or city positions, because they are concerned with issues that directly affect themselves and their well-being, as opposed to national politicians such as Senatorial or Presidential candidates (Cox & Mair, 1988; O'Neill & Hymel, 1995). While most past studies of the determinants of regulatory policymaking have concentrated on national-level issues (Blonigen, 2005), there is a more recent focus on state-level regulatory politics and the effectiveness of the legislative process in the current political, economic, and global environment. For example, most older literature related to the environment focused on national policies because it was taken for granted that environmental mandates were strictly enacted through federal mandates; however, environmental legislation and tactics to reduce greenhouse emissions are no longer merely a national issue.

For statewide regulation of environmental policies during the past decade, state politicians commonly utilized the principal-agent approach, in which the principal hires an agent to perform a task or undertake a project (Rabe, 2004). In this case, because the environmental policy domain is technical in nature, state and local politicians have enlisted expert bureaucrats and actors in environmental policy formation and implementation (Gerber and Teske, 2000). These agents play important roles in shaping their states. As a result, US political science and regulatory scholars now commonly employ state-level dynamics in their literature- because states and their proxies more often exert the most influence- as compared to the past when national politicians played a more central role. In addition to the devolution revolution, the nature of federalism within the US governmental system allows individual states considerable institutional diversity in their models of authority (Donovan, Mooney, &

Smith, 2009). Today, state legislatures and their proxies around the state are actively putting forth their own comprehensive packages that address statewide environmental policies.

Since state actors are responsive to problems specific to their jurisdictions, some states better protect the environment than would be the case if strict uniform national environmental standards were in place (Sapat, 2004). However, some states give little power to their environmental implementation agents and focus less on or are ambivalent about environmental regulations. Thus, not only does the US currently have different environmental laws than other countries, but today states within the US react differently to environmental concerns than other states.

The responsibility for environmental regulation has almost completely shifted from federal control to state control within one generation (Sapat, 2004), and this enhanced statewide clout has resulted in various levels of environmental regulation by state (Daley, Haider-Markel, & Whitford, 2007). Potoski and Woods (2002) confirmed that environmental policy now is situated at the state level, and individual states conduct enforcement actions that may or may not exceed US Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) minimum criteria, resulting in non-uniform air pollution regulations and air quality standards.

The nationwide decline in manufacturing has often necessitated that a state become active in economic development to replenish lost jobs. As the devolution revolution has allowed states to individually handle environmental concerns, state governments are realizing their increasing economic power. They are now utilizing proactive economic development actions in order to bring business to their states and are putting forth comprehensive packages that attract outside investment (Roberts, 2004).

For instance, in 1999, Indiana's General Assembly created The Indiana 21st-Century Research and Technology Fund, a state agent designed to help Hoosier businesses with technological and industrial potential apply for federal government innovation and research grants. In 2004, Jim Wheeler, executive director of Techpoint, an association of Indiana's high-tech companies said, "Over the last two years, the state has made more progress than it had in the previous eight or 10 years in terms of making the state more business-friendly" and cited the \$75 million allocated for the 21st-Century Research and Technology Fund in the first years of its existence as an example (McCurry, 2004). This organization awarded \$30 million in 2010, and in May, 2011, it was awarded an additional \$32.8 million dollars in grant money to Hoosier job creators (Heikens, 2011).

In recent years, lawmakers and organizations around the state have empowered another state agent, the Indiana Economic Development Corporation (IEDC), in efforts to preserve and enhance the manufacturing sector's contributions to the Hoosier economy. Created in 2004, the IEDC has worked to sustain manufacturing and to bring new industry to Indiana by providing incentives to domestic and international organizations. It has posted consecutive years of record-breaking commitments for new jobs (Journal Gazette, 2008), with about half of the state's new jobs in industry and the majority of those in the auto industry (IIB Report, 2011). In addition, the IEDC has been associated with more than \$18 billion in new investments in Indiana, with the bulk of these in industry (IIB Report, 2011). For instance, the cities of Marion and Kokomo received \$2 billion in automobile investments within two years (IIB Report5, 2011).

By 2010, the IEDC had signed 160 agreements promising 19,955 new jobs: in the first half of 2010, the IEDC secured 89 job-creation commitments from companies, creating 13,141 new jobs across the state (Schnitzler, 2010).

Other state organizations are designed to support Hoosier industry indirectly. The Indiana Department of Environmental Management assists Hoosier producers in pollution prevention after a first notice letter and receives grants from the Environmental Protection Agency to fund these actions (Klesmith & West, 2011). The Skills Enhancement Fund (SEF) provides financial assistance to businesses committed to training their workforce, and the Indiana Department of Workforce Development helps Hoosier companies with training, providing tax credits to hire new employees, and recruitment assistance (WorkOne, 2011).

Crandall (1993) found that there is no detriment in allowing states and municipalities to compete for manufacturing via the common methods of targeted infrastructure upgrades, tax incentives, and construction of industrial parks. This trend has prompted an all-out "arms race" between states to win the riches of incoming foreign direct investment directed at industry (Fleishmann, Green, & Kwong, 1988).

In general, states that commit resources and manpower to economic development organizations such as Indiana's IEDC tend to be the most likely to reel in the big catches of foreign industry in the twenty-first century. The "big catch" represents the great hope of a small or middle sized community that a major foreign industrial organization will commit to setting up operations and creating numerous jobs for the regional employment base (Deakin & Edwards, 1993).

Currently, many of the manufacturing jobs in Indiana are provided by internationally-based companies that have invested in the state. Indiana ranks sixth of all states in the ratio of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) to state Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and 65.8% of Hoosier FDI employment is based in manufacturing (FDI, 2008). Today, it is estimated that about 148,000 Hoosiers work for 700 global companies, mostly in the manufacturing sector (IIB Report2, 2011).

The Asia/Pacific share of FDI in Indiana is about one and a half times as much as its nationwide ratio (FDI, 2008). In particular, Japan is a major source of incoming FDI into Indiana, and many Japanese-owned factories have been operating in Indiana for quite some time. From 2005-2007, the IEDC negotiated 28 projects with Japanese businesses, which made Indiana the top state in Japanese-based jobs and investment captured during that time span. More than 220 Japanese companies invested more than \$8.7 billion in Indiana, and employed more than 42,000 Hoosiers (News Release, 2007).

The traditional importance of industry to the Hoosier economy is illustrated by incentives awarded to foreign investors for expansions and current global manufacturing facilities. The recent incentives offered by state actors have become more innovative and complex than the standard tax-incentive strategies that were first offered as bargaining chips in the 1980s.

Many political figures and politically-appointed organizations have the task of attracting new assembly operations to Indiana via these incentive strategies. The IEDC was especially instrumental in attracting and expanding Indiana's automobile industry in 2008 through incentives (IIB Report3, 2011; IIB Report 6, 2011). In one such case, in 2006, Toyota announced that their Lafayette-based Subaru plant would receive a \$230 million expansion and would add 1,000 jobs. This announcement marked the single largest job-creating initiative in the Lafayette area in 20 years (Expansion, 2007). The IEDC was influential in Toyota's decision, providing incentives such as \$500,000 in infrastructure upgrades to the area and \$1.25 million in training grants (Expansion, 2006).

In 2008, Indiana gained nearly 5,000 jobs created by foreign investment in expansions of existing automotive establishments and in Greenfield FDI investments. Most of this new employment was from multinational automobile manufacturers, an industry accounting for approximately 36 percent of all foreign-based Hoosier employment. In contrast, the share of new jobs in American automobile and auto-component manufacturing was 15 percent (InContext, 2008).

Another example of the importance of economic incentives to international manufacturing in Indiana involves the Japanese-based Sony operation. The Sony plant in Terre Haute is the only US-based Blu-ray assembly plant in North America. In the summer of 2008 after Blu-Ray seemed to win the victory over high-definition DVD's in the format war, Sony decided to invest more than \$113 million in the facility and to add 85 jobs. However, Sony needed governmental economic development signoffs to expand. The IEDC offered Sony up to \$975,000 in performance-based tax credits and up to \$655,000 in training grants and the Terre Haute City Council unanimously approved tax abatements for a \$72 million upgrade and the addition of 100 new jobs (WTHI, 2011). Sony in Terre Haute currently employs approximately 1,180 workers.

Factories like these make Japan an important cog in the Indiana economy. The importance of international investments to the Hoosier economy, particularly through Japanese and EU-owned manufacturing plants, cannot be underestimated. The growth of foreign industry will continue to play a key role in shaping the future of the manufacturing sector within the state of Indiana. However, the question of conflicting interests arises when the hope of engaging new industry at any costs clashes with environmental concerns.

This dilemma of economic development versus environmental regulation has gained salience as a result of the devolution revolution. Hicks (2009) discussed the public's definition of economic development versus the environment:

“Growth in per capita living standards is the classic definition. This is the simple ability to consume more goods and services. Adding to the value of our environment is also helpful. But in truth, most folks care about economic development as a verb, not a noun. (p. 2)”

Ecological modernization theory indicates that the environmental changes occurring in a society are greatly affected by the changing dynamics of newly empowered economic agents within a region, such as organizations designed to promote capital formation and job creation. The emergence of these new market forces in the US have come as a result of the devolution revolution, which may give rise to an aggressive, pro-business economic landscape which is lax in developing and enforcing environmental codes, both of which are run not by state government but by the state's implementing agents. As Indiana positions itself to be attractive to international capital and business, foreign manufacturing facilities that pollute the air might take advantage of a landscape in which the state is marketed as an attractive, pro-business setting with loose environmental standards. Especially since the IEDC is a taxpayer-funded organization and uses tax dollars for incentives, it may come under scrutiny if people perceive it as luring multinational industry at the cost of environmental standards.

Methods: EPA's Toxic Release Inventory

In his discussion of research into the ecological modernization theory, Mol (2003) stated that societal environmental evolution results in the creation and empowerment of key implementing agents that are designed to monitor and encourage policies and programs which arrest environmental degradation and improve environmental quality. These institutions might be international non-governmental organizations but might also include government-sponsored economic development organizations and government-sponsored EPA watchdogs (Hayter, 2004). One such watchdog in Indiana is the Toxic Release Inventory (TRI), which is a publicly-available EPA database that contains information on the release of toxic chemicals into the atmosphere and the waste management concentration activities reported annually by certain industries as well as federal facilities (EPA, 2010).

The most recent TRI data files from reporting year 2003 for the state of Indiana were examined to see if international manufacturing facilities tended to pollute more than domestic-based factories. Relevant information from the data files included the title of the certifying official, the name of the certifying official, date signed, facility name, information about the facility, the public contact name/info, and various detailed descriptions of the results of the test, including the types of chemicals that may or may not have been part of a factory's air pollution.

Nathan Byers (personal communication, 2010), from the Office of Pollution Prevention and Technical Assistance at the Indiana Department of Environmental Management, explained the various columns of the TRI spreadsheet. "Fugitive air emissions are all releases to air that are not released through a confined air stream. Fugitive emissions include equipment leaks, evaporative losses from surface impoundments and spills, and releases from building ventilation systems, from Section 5.1 on the TRI Form R" (Byers, 2010).

"However, different facilities have different ways of calculating emissions. Some are rates dependent on units of production, some on units of raw material, and some are a combination of both. And, some emissions go through a stack (point source) and some are not funneled through a stack (fugitive). Some facilities also have pollution control devices, and the air emissions reported in TRI are what is not captured by the devices (Total Emissions of VOCs = VOCs going in the front door - amount of VOCs captured by control devices)".

In order to compare apples to apples for air emissions, Byers suggested combining columns: "This will be taking into account what is leaving the facility via air no matter what the process is. In this way, you can fairly compare facilities in one industry to facilities in another". He indicated that the "Total Air Emissions" column was the combination of types of air leaving a facility.

As such, “Total Fugitive Air Emissions” and “Stack Air Emissions” were added to compute the “Total Air Emissions.” Thus, “Total Air Emissions” is the focus of comparison for this study. Many companies had multiple chemicals that were released as air emissions which were all included in their TRI report, so these total release pounds were added together to find a sum indicative of the combination of chemicals that each factory released into the air during the reporting year.

Several Hoosier company TRI representatives commented on the process of measuring air emissions. Maury Hoban (personal communication, 2010), of Federal-Mogul in South Bend, IN, described the process of measuring his company’s air emissions for the various chemicals used in their production process. According to the TRI, the six chemicals recorded at this plant were zinc compounds, nickel, manganese, lead, copper, and aluminum. Hoban does a stack test on the product in which “they do a controlled amount of metal melting and then equal that factor per pound or ton of emissions” and submits the results on a quarterly and annual basis to the state of Indiana. To assist with the testing process, Federal-Mogul hires an outside consulting firm that helps test emission factors based on the stack tests. “They go on the roof and make a special stack and put the probes there to measure the melting,” said Hoban. “They measure a controlled amount of melting for their tests.”

Charleston Corp. located in Bremen, IN, produces fiberglass parts for front end caps on recreational vehicles. Company TRI representative Shelley Miller (personal communication, 2010), who keeps track of purchase orders of the product and subsequent styrene emissions, described the process of measuring and tracking the amount of styrene emitted from their production process. “Our stack air emission is measured when resin is sprayed on with a spray gun in a specified exhaust area.”

The work done by these key implementation agents in Indiana allows the TRI to accurately track and publish air emissions put out by Hoosier manufacturing facilities.

Results: Comparing Air Emissions of Manufacturers Operating in Indiana

The TRI stated that there were 3,676 different types of chemicals utilized in the production of Indiana goods during the last reporting year. Those 3,676 chemicals released a specific amount of pounds into the air based on number of yearly units produced in a factory. In some instances, zero pounds of air emissions were released from the chemicals that were monitored.

To narrow down the large *n* using a non-biased, uniform method, manufacturers who emitted three or more chemicals into the air for a single production facility were identified as the sample set.

The next task of the data collection was to cluster Hoosier manufacturers by parent company location. The four classifications of Indiana-based producers whose parent company was located in 1) Indiana, 2) the EU, 3) Japan, and 4) other US states were determined. Table 1 shows below the breakdown of parent locations in the sample.

Table 1.

Number of Hoosier Producers Measured by Parent Location

Parent Location	# of companies measured
Indiana	16
EU	21
Japan	7
Other US States	113

Source: EPA’s Toxic Release Inventory

Table 2 below summarizes the two main categories of air emissions measurements as described by Byers (personal communication, 2010). The TRI categorized air pollution by pounds of “Fugitive air emissions” and “Stack air emissions”. Based on these categories of air pollution, both Indiana-based and other US state-based manufacturers tended to pollute at greater rates than those manufacturers whose parent company is located overseas. A separate category in the table determined the number of chemicals that emitted over 10 lbs. of air pollution from those factories.

Table 2.

Fugitive Emissions and Stack Emissions of Manufacturers by Parent Location

	Total Fugitive Air Emissions	Total Fugitive Air Emissions	# of chemicals releasing over 10 lbs. of fugitive air emissions	Total Stack Air Emissions	Total Stack Air Emissions	# of chemicals releasing over 10 lbs of stack air emissions
Producers operating in Indiana based in:	Avg. lbs	Total lbs		Avg. lbs	Total lbs	
Indiana (n=16)	21,989	329,839	113	368,557	5,528,360	

							151
EU (n=21)	5,750	120,759	83		41,420	869,822	120
Japan (n=7)	6,886	48,203	34		132,795	929,568	30
Other US States (n=113)	23,602	2,667,029	324		316,477	35,761,930	558

Source: EPA’s Toxic Release Inventory

These findings confirm that for the two major categories measuring air pollution, Fugitive Air Emissions and Stack Air Emissions, the Hoosier manufacturers whose home base is in Indiana or in other US states tend to put out more air emissions than those based in the EU and Japan. As discussed, “Total Air Emissions” can be determined when Fugitive Air Emissions and Stack Air Emissions are combined. Table 3 below shows those statistics. Also, the Total Air Emissions were divided by the number of factories to reflect the average pounds of Total Air Emissions that were emitted from each facility, as the table below displays.

Table 3.

Average Total Air Emissions of Hoosier Manufacturers, by Parent Location

Producers operating in Indiana based in:	Total Air Emissions: “Total” lbs.	Total Air Emissions: “Average” lbs.per factory
Indiana (n=16)	5,858,198	366,137
EU (n=21)	990,580	47,170
Japan (n=7)	977,771	139,682
Other US States (n=113)	38,428,959	340,079

Source: EPA’s Toxic Release Inventory

The figure below graphically depicts the average pounds of Total Air Emissions (Fugitive plus Stack air emissions) that were polluted into the Hoosier air for Indiana factories by parent location. The average pounds of air pollution by factory were highest in Indiana-based producers.

Figure 1.

Average Total Air Emissions of Hoosier Manufacturers, by Parent Location

Source: EPA's Toxic Release Inventory

Overall, the findings consistently indicate that when taking into account all current industrial production within the state, both Indiana-based and domestically-based manufacturers operating in Indiana tend to pollute the air at greater rates than both EU-based and Japanese-based Hoosier manufacturers.

Conclusion and Reactions

The devolution revolution and subsequent increased regulatory power of individual states creates a double-edged sword. Although it provides states like Indiana with more opportunities to create unique business incentives, it also introduces coinciding challenges, including the opportunity to shirk environmental mandates associated with production.

Based on the data found in this study, international manufacturers currently operating in Indiana appear to pollute the air at rates well below those of Indiana-based and domestically-based manufacturers. These results also underscore the notion that international manufacturers are generally better for Hoosier air quality than domestic organizations, based on recent rates of air pollution.

With the absence of broad, overreaching federal environmental mandates to adhere to, Indiana does have more leverage to allow pro-business policies, and it is fortunate that the IEDC does not need to rationalize why they are offering incentives to international manufacturers that tend to put out dangerous air emissions into the Hoosier sky at comparatively greater rates. In general, Indiana should continue to empower its key actors, including the IEDC, to actively solicit and enhance the manufacturing sector in the state. Since Indiana's economy is industry-based, Hoosier lawmakers and their agents should not assume that new industry will continue to locate within the state or that the jobs currently here will continue to operate. The IEDC should persist with their proactive approach to preserve and enhance the manufacturing sector's contributions to the Hoosier economy by marketing Indiana communities to international industry investment.

Further research involving the age of the factories included in this study would shed additional light on these emissions statistics. Certainly, the age of a factory is a determining factor in its emissions. Indiana-based factories might be older than the factories whose parent company is based overseas and therefore would pollute at rates more in line with less-modern facilities. However, it might be surmised that any future international capital investment in Indiana would provide similar air emissions numbers to those already in operation, since those manufacturing plants currently producing goods tend to be newer and/or more compliant with air emission standards. In addition, subsequent studies involving comparisons of similar industries across states would shed further light upon the current findings in an attempt to pinpoint discrepancies in factory emissions as they relate to the sector or industry-type. A comparison of manufacturers by industry-type would also provide a useful analysis.

Ecological modernization theory takes into account the key internal components that result in the net effect of how contemporary societies deal with environmental issues in their area. The various organizations that create environmental synergies (or lack of synergy) around the state ultimately determine the effectiveness of environmental legislation. Hoosier actors including the IEDC, state lawmakers, TRI participants, and legislative liaisons will continue to play a role in statewide air emission rates into the future and can point to the comparative

lack of pollution put out by international companies operating in Indiana. The IEDC therefore should be encouraged to continue its efforts to promote Indiana as a place to do business and a place that welcomes foreign industry.

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